

Design, synthesis, and anti-inflammatory activity of analogs of tetrapeptide Phe-Glu-Leu-Leu

Boryana Borisova^{1,2}, Veronica Nemska¹, Hristina Zlatanova-Tenisheva³, Marie Laronze-Cochard², Stéphane Gérard², Petya Romanova⁴, Anargyros N. Moulas⁵, Dancho Danalev¹

1 Biotechnology Department, University of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, 8 Kliment Ohridski blvd., 1797 Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Université de Reims Champagne-Ardenne, Institut de Chimie Moléculaire de Reims (ICMR) - UMR CNRS 7312, UFR de Pharmacie, 51 rue Cognacq-Jay - 51100 Reims, France

3 Department of Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Medical University of Plovdiv, 4002 Plovdiv, Bulgaria

4 Department of Engineering Ecology, University of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, 8 Kliment Ohridski blvd., 1797 Sofia, Bulgaria

5 University of Thessaly, Gaiopolis Campus, Perifereiaki Larisas Trikalon, Larissa, Greece

Corresponding author: Dancho Danalev (ddanalev@uctm.edu)

Received 1 May 2026 ♦ Accepted 15 June 2026 ♦ Published 2 July 2026

Citation: Borisova B, Nemska V, Zlatanova-Tenisheva H, Laronze-Cochard M, Gérard S, Romanova P, Moulas AN, Danalev D (2026) Design, synthesis, and anti-inflammatory activity of analogs of tetrapeptide Phe-Glu-Leu-Leu. *Pharmacia* 73: e198051. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e198051>

Abstract

Inflammation is part of the defense mechanism of the organism, which provokes different signaling pathways. It is also related to several inflammatory mediators, such as cytokines and enzymes from the phosphodiesterase group, especially phosphodiesterase 4 (PDE4). On the other hand, peptides play diverse physiological roles as neurotransmitters, neuromodulators, hormones, and enzyme modulators. Taking these facts into account, the anti-inflammatory activity of several C-terminal amide analogs of tetrapeptide Phe-Glu-Leu-Leu was investigated using the carrageenan-induced paw edema model, and their inhibitory activity against PDE4 was evaluated. It was found that Val and Ile substitutions at positions 3 and 4 improved anti-inflammatory activity *in vivo*, with compounds **BB3** and **BB4** producing statistically significant reductions in carrageenan-induced edema at the 3 h time point, although these effects were not sustained at later observations. However, the same substitutions did not consistently enhance PDE4 inhibition. The parent compounds **BB1** (C-terminal amide) and **BB11** (C-terminal free acid) demonstrated the most balanced overall profile, combining moderate PDE4 inhibitory activity (49% and 58% inhibition at a concentration of 5 mM, respectively) with favorable *in vivo* anti-inflammatory properties. These findings highlight the complex relationship between peptide structure, PDE4 inhibition, and anti-inflammatory efficacy.

Keywords

anti-inflammatory activity, C-terminal amides, FELL analogs, phosphodiesterase 4 inhibitory activity

Introduction

An essential immune response to harmful stimuli is inflammation. Such a defense mechanism is triggered by different pathogens, irritants, injuries, allergens, and toxins (Chen et al. 2017; National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences 2023). Furthermore, it provokes signaling pathways that initiate the healing process. The latter is expressed in two pathways, synthesizing anti-inflammatory mediators, such as cytokines, or suppressing pro-inflammatory ones, such as neutrophils and monocytes (Tavares et al. 2020; Li et al. 2023). Some of the mentioned stimuli result in acute or chronic inflammation, which causes cellular damage or other specific diseases as a secondary effect. Uncontrolled acute inflammation and inefficient treatment contribute to chronic diseases and could also lead to damage in a variety of organs. Such cellular damage, as well as the inflammation itself, is often characterized by pain, swelling, redness, and loss of some functions (Chen et al. 2017; Cohen et al. 2022).

Table 1. Mediators that regulate inflammatory response (Lawrence et al. 2002).

Mediator class	Pro-inflammatory	Anti-inflammatory
Amines	Histamine, bradykinin	Adrenaline, noradrenaline
Lipid mediators	PGE ₂ , PGI ₂ , LTB ₄ , LTC ₄	PGJ ₂ , PGA _{1/2}
Cyclic nucleotides	cGMP	cAMP
Cytokines	TNF, IL-1 β , IL-6	TGF-1 β , IL10
Chemokines	IL-8, MCP1, MIP1 α	-
Steroid hormones	-	Glucocorticoids

One of these mediators that possesses anti-inflammatory properties is intracellular cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP). In recent decades, cAMP has been recognized as an important intracellular second messenger that reduces the activation of immune cells, such as leukocytes, neutrophils, and macrophages. Under physiological conditions, intracellular cAMP levels are strictly maintained by a balance between synthesis catalyzed by adenylyl cyclases (AC) and degradation by phosphodiesterases (PDEs). In their review, Tavares et al. summarized both *in vivo* and *in vitro* evidence supporting the conclusion that high levels of cAMP can suppress immune and non-immune inflammatory responses (Tavares et al. 2020). Thus, the development of novel PDE inhibitors that influence intracellular cAMP levels might be a promising basis for the creation of a new class of anti-inflammatory therapeutics. Among all 11 families of PDEs, PDE4 has generated high interest because it is overexpressed in inflammatory cells, such as neutrophils (Dunne et al. 2019), monocytes and macrophages (Banner and Press 2009), airway smooth muscle (Raker et al. 2016), and fibroblasts (Selige et al. 2011), and could most strongly influence the inflammation process by participating in the regulation of cAMP levels. As the PDE4 family encompasses four genes coding the subtypes PDE4A–D, the PDE4B subtype is

believed to play a central role in inflammation, being the predominant subtype in monocytes and neutrophils, particularly at the pulmonary level, making it a therapeutic target for the treatment of asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Chronic inflammation cases have tended to increase in recent years and are additionally influenced by various contemporary factors, such as more infections arising from higher antimicrobial resistance, exposure to ever-changing environmental conditions, lifestyle behaviors, dietary patterns, psychological stress, and chemical agents. The leading described causes of disability worldwide are cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, and autoimmune and neurodegenerative disorders (Furman et al. 2019). The most widespread treatments for managing acute and chronic inflammation include glucocorticoids and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Despite their effectiveness, these drugs are associated with a broad spectrum of adverse effects, including delayed wound healing, gastrointestinal toxicity, cardiovascular complications, renal injury, and cerebral complications (Ramamoorthy and Cidlowski 2016; Bindu et al. 2020). In recent years, advanced research has developed antibodies targeting specific cytokines and interleukins as promising alternatives. Some representatives of these anti-TNF agents are infliximab, adalimumab, and etanercept. They have significantly improved the management of autoimmune and inflammatory diseases by inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α . However, despite their initial efficacy, long-term results reveal a decreased therapeutic response due to immunogenicity and treatment resistance (Li 2017). Thus, another promising alternative to conventional anti-inflammatory therapies is anti-inflammatory peptides (AIPs), which are low-toxicity compounds with natural mechanisms for inflammation elimination in the human organism, isolated from different natural sources (Liu et al. 2022; Tonolo et al. 2025) or obtained synthetically (Manna et al. 2018). Currently, they are largely studied due to their therapeutic advantages, such as high specificity for binding specific enzymes and receptors, as well as their low toxicity (Castrellon et al. 2025; Liu et al. 2025).

Bioactive peptides (BPs) have relatively short chains, typically less than 50 amino acids, that exert specific biological effects within living cells and organisms (Wang et al. 2022; Fetse et al. 2023). These peptides play important roles in regulating various physiological processes and have been shown to exhibit a wide range of effects, including antihypertensive, antimicrobial, antithrombotic, immunomodulatory, cholesterol-lowering, and anti-inflammatory effects (Alzaydi et al. 2023; Biji et al. 2024). Furthermore, some of them have demonstrated antioxidant properties (Chakrabarti et al. 2014), which help prevent the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that contribute to various chronic and acute inflammatory disorders. BPs have gained significant attention as potential therapeutic agents due to their small size, natural biodegradability, and minimal side effects. Unlike many conventional medications associated with long-term adverse

effects, BPs often exhibit higher specificity and improved safety profiles and are easily metabolized and eliminated by the organism (Dadar et al. 2019; Biji et al. 2024). Thus, BPs are highly suitable for long-term use in treating chronic diseases, such as inflammation. In their scientific review, Dadar et al. highlighted several AIPs derived from different natural sources (Dadar et al. 2019). Plant-, animal-, marine-, and human-origin sources are mentioned as bases for developing novel classes of AIPs. Attention was drawn to three peptides derived from human calcium-binding protein spermatid-specific 1 (CABS1), named FELL, TDIFELL, and TDIFELLK. The latter were first studied and evaluated for their activity *in vivo* in the research of Laurent et al. in 2015 (St. Laurent et al. 2015). The anti-inflammatory effects were demonstrated during these investigations in an *in vivo* mouse model of lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-induced neutrophilia, as well as in an *ex vivo* rat model of antigen-induced intestinal anaphylaxis. In the LPS-induced model, all peptides showed greater efficacy than the control AIM-102. They reduced white blood cell (WBC) accumulation in the bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) by 52–56%, compared to 39% for AIM-102 at a dose of 5 mg/kg. The affected cells from the WBC population were only neutrophils and macrophages – an indication of the anti-inflammatory activity of the peptides. Additionally, in the *ex vivo* model, two of these peptide sequences, FELL and TDIFELLK, significantly inhibited ileal contractions at concentrations of 10^{-6} M and 10^{-7} M. Based on these results, the authors postulated that the shortest FELL sequence may be the core motif responsible for the observed activity and suggested that it could exert anti-inflammatory effects in additional experimental assays and disease models.

In prior research, four new FELL (Phe¹-Glu²-Leu³-Leu⁴) analogs were synthesized by modification of the amino acid sequence in the 3rd and 4th positions, as well as by amidation of the C-terminus (Borisova et al. 2023). Leu was replaced with different hydrophobic amino acids in the 3rd and 4th positions (Nle, Ile, or Val) to study the role of hydrophobicity in analgesic properties in a paw pressure threshold (PPT) test. The obtained results showed that all newly synthesized peptides exhibited analgesia by different mechanisms. The parent peptide FELL, as well as the C-terminal amidated analog FELL-NH₂, was the best choice for lasting analgesia over the 50 min test period. However, the analog with a Val residue, FEVV-NH₂, showed the highest activity, but only during the first 10 min of the experiment. Based on the postulation in the research of Laurent et al. (St. Laurent et al. 2015) and the role of inflammatory mediators, as summarized by Tavares and co-workers and Lawrence et al. (Lawrence et al. 2002; Tavares et al. 2020;), an *in vitro* study was conducted herein to evaluate anti-inflammatory potential by means of a carrageenan-induced paw edema model, as well as by testing PDE4B inhibition capability. PDE4B inhibition may hypothetically increase intracellular cAMP levels – a key regulator known to increase anti-inflammatory mediators.

Abbreviations

PDE4	phosphodiesterase 4
PDE4B	phosphodiesterase 4 subtype B
PG	prostaglandin
LT	leukotriene
cGMP	cyclic guanosine-3,5-monophosphate
TNF	tumor-necrosis factor
TGF-β1	transforming growth factor-β1
I	interleukin
MCP1α	monocyte chemotactic protein 1
MIP1α	macrophage inflammatory protein 1α
cAMP	cyclic adenosine monophosphate
AC	adenylyl cyclases
AIPs	anti-inflammatory peptides
ROS	reactive oxygen species
BPs	bioactive peptides
CABS1	calcium-binding protein spermatid-specific 1
LPS	lipopolysaccharide

Materials and methods

Synthesis of target peptides

All target peptides were synthesized by standard solid-phase peptide synthesis (SPPS)/Fmoc-/OtBu strategy on Fmoc-Rink Amide MBHA using standard protocols for activation with *N,N'*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC) or 2-(1*H*-benzotriazole-1-yl)-1,1,3,3-tetramethylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TBTU) (Borisova et al. 2023, 2024, 2025).

Anti-inflammatory activity

Experimental animals

The study was conducted using 6-week-old male Wistar rats, each weighing 150–200 g. The animals were randomly divided into 10 experimental groups, with eight rats per group. The group size was selected based on previous experience with the carrageenan-induced paw edema model and published studies employing similar experimental designs. They were maintained under standard laboratory conditions, including a controlled temperature, a 12 h light/dark cycle, and unrestricted access to food and water. All procedures for assessing anti-inflammatory activity were approved by the Animal Health and Welfare Directorate of the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, following the recommendation of the Ethics Committee, Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (Protocol No. 419/20.12.2024).

Carrageenan-induced paw edema

Baseline measurements of the right hind paw volume were taken for all animals before any treatment. Edema was induced by injecting 0.1 mL of 1% carrageenan solution in 0.9% sodium chloride into the right hind paw. Control animals received an intraperitoneal injection of 0.1 mL of 0.9% sodium chloride immediately

after carrageenan administration. Positive control animals were treated with diclofenac at a dose of 25 mg/kg body weight, while the experimental groups received the test peptides at a dose of 2 mg/kg body weight via intraperitoneal injection. Investigators performing paw volume measurements were blinded to treatment allocation throughout the experiment to minimize measurement bias.

Paw volume was subsequently measured using a plethysmometer (Ugo Basile, Italy) at 2, 3, and 4 h after carrageenan injection. Paw edema was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Paw edema (\%)} = ((V_t - V_0) / V_0) * 100 \quad (1)$$

where

- V_0 = mean paw volume before treatment
- V_t = mean paw volume at each time point

A decrease in paw swelling relative to the control group was considered indicative of anti-inflammatory activity.

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26.0. One-way ANOVA was applied, followed by Tukey or Games-Howell post hoc tests depending on the outcomes of Levene's test for homogeneity of variances and Welch and Brown-Forsythe tests for equality of means. The normality of data distribution was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Results are presented as the arithmetic mean \pm standard error of the mean (mean \pm SEM), with statistical significance defined as $p \leq 0.05$.

PDE4 inhibitory activity

The ability of newly synthesized FELL analogs to inhibit PDE4 activity was determined using a cyclic nucleotide phosphodiesterase assay kit (Enzo Life Sciences, France) (Allart-Simon et al. 2021). All FELL analogs were previously dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and their 50 mM stock solutions were stored in a refrigerator at -20 °C. A 5 μ L aliquot of the peptide solution (5 mM per well) was incubated in a 96-well polystyrene microplate (Deltalab S.L., Barcelona, Spain), containing a mixture of 30 μ L PDE assay buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4), 5 μ L PDE4B enzyme, 5 μ L cAMP, and 5 μ L 5'-nucleotidase at 35 °C for 60 min. The assay is based on the sequential cleavage of cAMP with cyclic nucleotide PDE and 5'-nucleotidase to the final products nucleoside and phosphate. The reaction was terminated by the addition of 100 μ L of BIOMOL GREEN reagent, followed by incubation of the microplate at room temperature for an additional 30 min to allow color development. The optical density of samples at 630 nm was measured with a SPECTROstar Nano microplate reader (BMG LABTECH, Germany), and the results were expressed as % inhibition of PDE4B. The nonspecific PDE inhibitor IBMX was used as a test control for inhibitor screening. All experiments were conducted in triplicate.

Results

Evaluation of the anti-inflammatory activity of the FELL analogs

Synthesis of all target peptides was previously described (Borisova et al. 2023, 2024, 2025). Briefly, the first amino acid in the C-terminus, Leu, was attached to Rink Amide MBHA Resin purchased from Iris Biotech GmbH (Marktredwitz, Germany). Further, all other amino acids were added to the peptide chain from the C- to N-terminus consecutively. The condensation step was performed using DIC or TBTU as activation agents in a molar ratio of 3/3/3/9/1 for amino acid/TBTU/DIPEA/resin or 3/3/3/1 for amino acid/DIC/1-HOSu/resin. Final peptides were obtained after treatment with a cocktail containing 95% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA), 2.5% triisopropylsilane (TIS), and 2.5% distilled water as crude oil, which was crystallized after treatment with cold, dry diethyl ether. All structures were proven by MS and the purity by HPLC. The peptides were subjected to the following biological tests with a minimum of 95% chromatographic purity.

In the carrageenan-induced paw edema test, the untreated control group displayed consistently high percentages of edema across all observed time points, with values declining only slightly from 82.40% at the 2nd hour to 72.61% at the 4th hour. This confirmed the expected progressive but incomplete natural resolution of inflammation in the absence of treatment. By contrast, diclofenac – the standard anti-inflammatory reference drug – demonstrated a pronounced and sustained inhibitory effect on edema formation. Edema levels in this group remained consistently low, ranging between 13.04% and 15.19% across the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th hours, with all comparisons to the control group being highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This finding reinforced the reliability of diclofenac as a positive control and benchmark for assessing the anti-inflammatory potential of the test compounds.

BB2, where Leu residues in positions 3 and 4 of parent compound **BB11** were replaced with spatially unconstrained nor-Leu residues, showed no reduction in edema at any point in time, with values ranging from 89.23% to 92.23%, remaining statistically indistinguishable from

Table 2. Primary structures of tested compounds.

Entry	Peptide code	Corresponding peptide structure*
1	BB1 /parent amide analog/	FELL-NH ₂
2	BB2	FEnLnL-NH ₂
3	BB3	FEVV-NH ₂
4	BB4	FEII-NH ₂
5	BB5	fELL-NH ₂
6	BB5'	fELL-NH ₂
7	BB7	fEII-NH ₂
8	BB8	fEVV-NH ₂
9	BB11 /parent peptide/	FELL-OH

*D-enantiomers of amino acids used are noted with lowercase letters.

Table 3. Comparison of the percentage of edema in the carrageenan-induced paw edema test between the control group and the groups treated with diclofenac and test substances.

Group	Hour	mean \pm SEM	<i>p</i>	Group	Hour	mean \pm SEM	<i>p</i>
Control	2 nd	82.40 \pm 4.46	–	BB5	2 nd	82.92 \pm 12.17	1.000
	3 rd	80.39 \pm 3.40			3 rd	102.41 \pm 11.38	0.655
	4 th	72.61 \pm 3.95			4 th	86.69 \pm 10.74	0.976
Diclofenac	2 nd	13.90 \pm 2.33	<0.001*	BB5'	2 nd	86.43 \pm 13.46	1.000
	3 rd	15.19 \pm 2.49	<0.001*		3 rd	98.17 \pm 18.24	0.980
	4 th	13.04 \pm 3.46	<0.001*		4 th	99.58 \pm 14.28	0.514
BB2	2 nd	89.23 \pm 12.78	1.000	BB7	2 nd	71.84 \pm 6.9	0.996
	3 rd	106.22 \pm 13.82	0.676		3 rd	92.82 \pm 6.3	0.717
	4 th	92.23 \pm 10.15	0.855		4 th	88.58 \pm 8.73	0.950
BB3	2 nd	74.4 \pm 11.26	1.000	BB8	2 nd	98.08 \pm 4.64	0.956
	3 rd	41.28 \pm 6.98	0.034*		3 rd	85.22 \pm 4.99	0.995
	4 th	47.86 \pm 8.29	0.578		4 th	99.63 \pm 9.52	0.512
BB4	2 nd	63.99 \pm 8.99	0.943				
	3 rd	43.21 \pm 6.45	0.029*				
	4 th	47.48 \pm 5.58	0.175				

the control (all $p > 0.6$). Similarly, **BB5'** and the more hydrophobic derivative **BB5** (containing one more Leu residue in the peptide chain, together with *D*-Phe in the first position in place of the L-stereoisomer) maintained edema levels close to those of the untreated control, with no significant inhibitory activity observed throughout the experiment. The analogs **BB7**, where Leu residues in the parent compound were replaced by their structural analogs Ile, and **BB8**, with Val residues in positions 3 and 4 and *D*-Phe in the first position of the peptide chain (Table 2), also failed to produce measurable anti-inflammatory effects, with mean values at all time points fluctuating approximately 72–99% and no significant differences relative to the control group.

In contrast, **BB3** and **BB4**, containing the same substitutions of Leu in the parent molecule with Val and Ile residues, respectively, but retaining L-Phe in their first positions, demonstrated partial but noteworthy anti-inflammatory activity. At the 2nd hour, neither compound significantly reduced edema compared to the control (74.40% for **BB3** and 63.99% for **BB4**, both with $p > 0.9$). However, by the 3rd hour, a substantial reduction was observed: **BB3** lowered edema to 41.28% ($p = 0.034$) and **BB4** to 43.21% ($p = 0.029$). These effects were comparable in magnitude and suggested that both compounds may exert a time-dependent inhibitory action on carrageenan-induced inflammation. At the 4th hour, however, the edema percentages rebounded somewhat (to 47.86% for **BB3** and 47.48% for **BB4**), and statistical significance was lost. Thus, while both **BB3** and **BB4** demonstrated a clear anti-inflammatory effect at the intermediate time point, the effect appeared transient rather than sustained.

Taken together, these findings confirm the robust anti-inflammatory action of diclofenac and suggest moderate, time-specific efficacy for **BB3** and **BB4**, which achieved significant reductions at the 3rd hour but not beyond. By contrast, **BB2**, **BB5**, **BB5'**, **BB7**, and **BB8** were largely inactive. These results provide an important basis for further

investigation into the structure–activity relationships of these compounds, particularly **BB3** and **BB4**, as potential candidates for anti-inflammatory development. Table 3 compares the percentage of edema in the carrageenan-induced paw edema test across experimental groups.

Evaluation of the PDE4 inhibitory activity

The effects of peptides on the modulation of the intracellular level of cyclic AMP were then examined and compared to those of the nonspecific PDE inhibitor 3-isobutyl-1-methylxanthine (IBMX) and a therapeutic reference in inflammatory diseases, roflumilast. All the synthesized FELL analogs were preliminarily screened in a nonradioactive assay developed in the laboratory for the selection of privileged structures. The percentage of PDE4 inhibition at a 5 mM concentration of target peptides is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Percentage of PDE4 inhibition at 5 mM concentration of targeted peptides.

Entry	Peptide code	Corresponding peptide structure	% of inhibition at 5 mM*
1	BB1 /parent amide analog/	FELL-NH ₂	49%
2	BB2	FEnLnL-NH ₂	No inhibition detected
3	BB3	FEVV-NH ₂	26 \pm 1%
1	BB4	FEII-NH ₂	50 \pm 3%
5	BB5	fELL-NH ₂	67 \pm 1%
6	BB5'	fELL-NH ₂	62 \pm 2%
7	BB7	fEII-NH ₂	46 \pm 1%
8	BB8	fEVV-NH ₂	43 \pm 2%
9	BB11 /parent peptide/	FELL-OH	58 \pm 1%
10	IBMX		38 \pm 2%
11	Roflumilast		75 \pm 1%

*The data are the average values of three different measurements of inhibition.

Discussion

Peptide synthesis

Target peptides were synthesized following the general scheme presented in Fig. 1.

The synthesis of the target peptides was designed to yield 0.1 g of final product. Each synthesis was carried out in a 20 mL glass manual reactor using Rink Amide MBHA resin (loading capacity: 0.63 mmol/g, 200–400 mesh) to generate peptides as C-terminal amides. The initial amino acid, as well as each subsequent residue, was coupled following standard SPPS condensation protocols. Fmoc deprotection was performed with 20% piperidine in DMF. For the activation of the amino acid, 3 eq. of HBTU in the presence of 9 eq. of DIPEA were used for preliminary activation for a 20-min period. If DIC was used as an activation agent, a ratio of 3/3/3/1 for amino acid/DIC/1-HOSu/resin was respected. The resulting solution was then transferred to the glass manual reactor containing the deprotected peptide-resin. The mixture was stirred for up to 6 h. The successful reaction was confirmed by a negative Kaiser test, indicating the absence of color in the resin beads. After each step, the resin-peptide was washed thoroughly with 2×10 mL DMF and 2×10 mL DCM to remove residual piperidine and by-products.

Cleavage from the resin was achieved by stirring for 3.5 h in TFA/TIS/H₂O (95:2.5:2.5). After the reaction time, the resin beads were removed by filtration through a fine-sintered glass funnel, and the filtrate was concentrat-

ed under reduced pressure. Residual TFA was eliminated by repeated co-evaporation with an *n*-hexane/DCM (1:1) azeotropic mixture. The crude peptides, obtained as oily residues, were subsequently precipitated as solids by adding them to cold, dry diethyl ether.

Anti-inflammatory activity

FELL, TDIFELL, and TDIFELLK are several peptide derivatives from human calcium-binding protein spermatid-specific 1 (CABS1). First, they were investigated by Laurent et al. (St. Laurent et al. 2015), and their anti-inflammatory effects were revealed in two animal models. In addition to their discovered anti-inflammatory effect, they found that it was due to the core motif FELL. Thus, specific *in vivo* tests in a mouse model showed that FELL reduces the number of white blood cells in bronchoalveolar fluid more than the control AIM-102 (51% vs. 39%). Taking into account all these results, the anti-inflammatory activity of the C-terminal amide analogs of the tetrapeptide Phe-Glu-Leu-Leu (FELL-NH₂) in the carrageenan-induced paw edema model demonstrated variable efficacy across the series, with a pattern that only partially correlates with their PDE4 inhibitory profiles. Although PDE4 inhibition is widely recognized as a relevant anti-inflammatory mechanism through elevation of intracellular cAMP and subsequent suppression of immune cell activation and pro-inflammatory signaling (Tavares et al. 2020; Fetse et al. 2023), the present findings clearly indicate that enzymatic inhibition alone is not sufficient to predict *in vivo* efficacy.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the general SPPS cycle.

Among the tested compounds, **BB3** (FEVV-NH₂) and **BB4** (FEII-NH₂) exhibited the most notable anti-edematous effects at the 3rd hour, reducing paw edema to 41.28% ($p = 0.034$) and 43.21% ($p = 0.029$), respectively. This indicates a moderate, time-dependent anti-inflammatory effect, although the lack of sustained activity at the 4th hour suggests a transient pharmacodynamic profile. Notably, **BB4** demonstrated relatively strong PDE4 inhibition (50% at 5 mM), whereas **BB3** showed considerably lower inhibition (26%), indicating that PDE4 inhibition contributes to activity but does not solely determine *in vivo* efficacy (Fetse et al. 2023).

The observed *in vitro*–*in vivo* discrepancy can be attributed to several complementary factors. First, differences in peptide physicochemical properties, including hydrophobicity, stereochemistry, and conformational flexibility, likely affect tissue distribution and stability under physiological conditions. Carrageenan-induced inflammation is strongly dependent on local vascular permeability and proteolytic environments, which may differentially degrade or inactivate peptides before reaching effective concentrations at the site of action (Alzaydi et al. 2023). Second, structural modifications, such as the incorporation of Val or Ile residues in **BB3** and **BB4**, appear to enhance transient biological activity, suggesting that side-chain stericity and hydrophobic interactions may influence membrane association and local bioavailability (Biji et al. 2024). In contrast, analogs containing *D*-amino acids in the N-terminal position or extended hydrophobic substitutions (e.g., **BB5**, **BB5'**, **BB7**, **BB8**) may exhibit altered conformations that improve enzymatic stability but reduce functional interaction with relevant biological targets *in vivo*.

Importantly, the PDE4 inhibition data do not fully align with the observed *in vivo* outcomes. **BB5** (fELL-NH₂) and **BB5'** (fELL-NH₂) exhibited relatively high PDE4 inhibition (67% and 62%, respectively) yet failed to reduce edema *in vivo*. However, the PDE4 inhibition activity of both the **BB5** and **BB5'** analogs clearly shows that the higher hydrophobicity of the peptide is a key factor for a better effect on the target enzyme. Conversely, **BB3** showed modest PDE4 inhibition but measurable anti-inflammatory activity. This further supports the notion that *in vitro* PDE4 inhibition is not a sufficient predictor of systemic anti-inflammatory efficacy (Borisova et al. 2025). Inhibition of PDE4 is expected to attenuate inflammatory responses by increasing intracellular cAMP levels, thereby suppressing immune cell activation and reducing the release of pro-inflammatory and profibrotic cytokines, ultimately limiting fibroblast activation and extracellular matrix deposition (Chakrabarti et al. 2014; St. Laurent et al. 2015; Dadar et al. 2019; Borisova et al. 2023, 2024). However, the present data suggest that additional mechanisms, including peptide stability, cellular uptake, and possible interactions with non-PDE4 inflammatory pathways, likely contribute to the observed pharmacological effects. Measurement of the inhibition of pro-inflammatory cytokine secretion by peptides **BB3** and **BB4** in comparison with other analogs will confirm these preliminary results.

All other peptides (**BB2**, **BB5**, **BB5'**, **BB7**, and **BB8**) did not significantly reduce edema at any time point,

maintaining levels comparable to the control. Their PDE4 inhibitory activities varied widely: **BB2** showed no measurable inhibition, whereas **BB5** and **BB5'** demonstrated strong enzymatic inhibition (67% and 62%, respectively, compared to roflumilast), further emphasizing the disconnect between *in vitro* enzyme inhibition and *in vivo* functional response (Borisova et al. 2025). The parent compounds, **BB1** (FELL-NH₂) and **BB11** (FELL-OH), exhibited moderate PDE4 inhibition (49% and 58%, respectively), suggesting that minimal structural modification preserves a more balanced relationship between enzymatic activity and biological effect (Allart-Simon et al. 2021).

Overall, the data highlight that while PDE4 inhibition contributes to anti-inflammatory potential, it is not sufficient on its own to predict *in vivo* outcomes. The transient anti-inflammatory effects of **BB3** and **BB4**, the lack of *in vivo* efficacy of highly PDE4-active analogs, and the overall structure-dependent variability underscore the importance of integrating structural considerations, enzymatic profiling, and *in vivo* functional testing when evaluating peptide-based anti-inflammatory candidates. These findings illustrate a complex interplay between peptide structure, PDE4 inhibition, and immunomodulatory activity, providing important insights for the optimization of tetrapeptide analogs as potential anti-inflammatory therapeutics.

A number of limitations should be acknowledged in the present study. First, PDE4 inhibitory activity was assessed at a single concentration (5 mM), which does not allow determination of IC₅₀ values and therefore prevents quantitative comparison of potency among the peptide analogs. This also limits the strength of any direct correlation between enzymatic inhibition and *in vivo* anti-inflammatory effects. Second, peptide stability and bioavailability were not experimentally evaluated and may have significantly influenced the observed outcomes, as peptides are generally susceptible to rapid enzymatic degradation *in vivo* and may differ in their ability to reach effective concentrations at the site of inflammation depending on structural modifications. Accordingly, improved *in vitro* enzymatic activity does not necessarily translate into enhanced *in vivo* efficacy. Finally, the *in vivo* experiments were limited to a 2–4 h observation window, which mainly reflects the acute inflammatory phase in the carrageenan model. Therefore, potential delayed, prolonged, or resolution-phase effects beyond 4–6 h were not assessed, and possible sustained anti-inflammatory actions of the tested peptides may have been underestimated.

Conclusion

The present structure–activity relationship (SAR) study of FELL tetrapeptide analogs demonstrates that amino acid substitutions modulate both PDE4 inhibitory activity and *in vivo* anti-inflammatory effects; however, a clear discrepancy between *in vitro* enzyme inhibition and *in vivo* efficacy was observed, highlighting the multifactorial nature of peptide activity:

- The introduction of a *D*-amino acid at the N-terminus, combined with substitutions at positions 3 and 4, resulted in low to moderate PDE4 inhibition (<50–70%), but these changes did not consistently improve *in vivo* anti-inflammatory effects, suggesting that enzymatic potency alone is not predictive of biological activity. This is consistent with previous analgesic findings for the same series (Borisova et al. 2025).
- Val- and Ile-containing analogs, represented by **BB3** and **BB4**, demonstrated the most pronounced anti-inflammatory effects in the carrageenan-induced paw edema model, producing statistically significant reductions in edema at the 3 h time point. However, these effects were transient and were not maintained at the 4 h observation period.

Overall, the parent compounds **BB1** (C-terminal amide) and **BB11** (C-terminal free acid) exhibited the most balanced profile, combining moderate PDE4 inhibition with favorable overall pharmacological properties, including previously reported analgesic activity (Borisova et al. 2025). These findings suggest that minimal structural modification of the FELL scaffold may be preferable for maintaining a favorable balance between enzymatic and *in vivo* activity.

Further studies are required to validate the proposed structure–activity relationships, including cytokine profiling, dose–response investigations, peptide stability assessments, pharmacokinetic characterization, and evaluation in additional models of inflammation.

References

- Allart-Simon I, Moniot A, Bisi N, Ponce-Vargas M, Audonnet S, Laronze-Cochard M, Sapi J, Hénon E, Velard F, Gérard S (2021) Pyridazinone derivatives as potential anti-inflammatory agents: synthesis and biological evaluation as PDE4 inhibitors. *RSC Medicinal Chemistry* 12: 584–592. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0md00423e>
- Alzaydi A, Barbhuiya RI, Routray W, Elsayed A, Singh A (2023) Bioactive peptides: Synthesis, applications, and associated challenges. *Food Bioengineering* 2: 273–290. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fbe2.12057>
- Banner KH, Press NJ (2009) Dual PDE3/4 inhibitors as therapeutic agents for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *British Journal of Pharmacology* 157: 892–906. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.2009.00170.x>
- Biji CA, Balde A, Nazeer RA (2024) Anti-inflammatory peptide therapeutics and the role of sulphur containing amino acids (cysteine and methionine) in inflammation suppression: A review. *Inflammation Research* 73: 1203–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-024-01893-6>
- Bindu S, Mazumder S, Bandyopadhyay U (2020) Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and organ damage: A current perspective. *Biochemical Pharmacology* 180: 114147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcp.2020.114147>
- Borisova B, Nocheva H, Zlatanova-Tenisheva H, Laronze-Cochard M, Gérard S, Danalev D (2025) Synthesis and biological study of novel FELL analogs containing L- or d-tyr instead of l-phe in the N-terminus. *Current Research in Biotechnology*: 100332. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbiot.2025.100332>
- Borisova B, Nocheva H, Iliev I, Laronze-Cochard M, Gérard S, Petrin S, Danalev D (2024) Synthesis and analgesic activity of new analogs of FELL tetrapeptide containing D-Phe in the first position. *Current Research in Biotechnology* 8: 100249. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbiot.2024.100249>
- Borisova B, Nocheva H, Gérard S, Laronze-Cochard M, Dobrev S, Angelova S, Petrin S, Danalev D (2023) Synthesis, In Silico Logp Study, and In Vitro Analgesic Activity of Analogs of Tetrapeptide FELL. *Pharmaceuticals* 16: 1183. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph16081183>
- Castrellon PG, Lernhardt W, Jenkins I, Casazza K, Robinson B, Mathur E, Andrade D, Uffens J, Andrade-Platas D, Medina-Nolasco A, Lakey JRT (2025) Safety and Efficacy of Peptide-Based Therapeutics in Health Sciences: From Bench to Bedside. *American Journal of Biomedical Science and Research* 28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-026-02437-0>
- Chakrabarti S, Jahandideh F, Wu J (2014) Food-derived bioactive peptides on inflammation and oxidative stress. *BioMed Research International* 2014: 608979. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/608979>
- Chen L, Deng H, Cui H, Fang J, Zuo Z, Deng J, Li Y, Wang X, Zhao L (2017) Inflammatory responses and inflammation-associated diseases in organs. *Oncotarget* 9: 7204–7218. <https://doi.org/10.18632/oncotarget.23208>
- Cohen SP, Wang EJ, Doshi TL, Vase L, Cawcutt KA, Tontisirin N (2022) Chronic pain and infection: mechanisms, causes, conditions, treatments, and controversies. *BMJ Medicine* 1. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjmed-2021-000108>
- Dadar M, Shahali Y, Chakraborty S, Prasad M, Tahoori F, Tiwari R, Dharma K (2019) Antiinflammatory peptides: current knowledge and promising prospects. *Inflammation Research* 68: 125–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00011-018-1208-x>
- Dunne AE, Kawamatawong T, Fenwick PS, Davies CM, Tullett H, Barnes PJ, Donnelly LE (2019) Direct Inhibitory Effect of the PDE4 Inhibitor Roflumilast on Neutrophil Migration in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. *American Journal of Respiratory Cell and Molecular Biology* 60: 445–453. <https://doi.org/10.1165/rcmb.2018-0065OC>
- Fetse J, Kandel S, Mamani U-F, Cheng K (2023) Recent advances in the development of therapeutic peptides. *Trends in Pharmacological Sciences* 44: 425–441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tips.2023.04.003>
- Furman D, Campisi J, Verdin E, Carrera-Bastos P, Targ S, Franceschi C, Ferrucci L, Gilroy DW, Fasano A, Miller GW, Miller AH, Mantovani A, Weyand CM, Barzilai N, Goronzy JJ, Rando TA, Effros RB, Lucia A, Kleinstreuer N, Slavich GM (2019) Chronic inflammation in the etiology of disease across the life span. *Nature Medicine* 25: 1822–1832. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-019-0675-0>
- Lawrence T, Willoughby DA, Gilroy DW (2002) Anti-inflammatory lipid mediators and insights into the resolution of inflammation. *Nature Reviews. Immunology* 2: 787–795. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nri915>
- Li JJ (2017) Synthesis of Best-Seller Drugs. By Ruben Vardanyan and Victor Hruby. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 56: 2541–2541. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201700015>
- Li X, Li C, Zhang W, Wang Y, Qian P, Huang H (2023) Inflammation and aging: signaling pathways and intervention therapies. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy* 8: 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-023-01502-8>

- Liu M, Svirskis D, Proft T, Loh J, Yin N, Li H, Li D, Zhou Y, Chen S, Song L, Chen G, Lu W-Y, Zhang Z, Zhou Z, Li L, Huang Y, Bunt C, Sun G, Harris PWR, Brimble MA, Wen J (2025) Progress in peptide and protein therapeutics: Challenges and strategies. *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica. B* 15: 6342–6381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsb.2025.10.026>
- Liu W, Chen X, Li H, Zhang J, An J, Liu X (2022) Anti-Inflammatory Function of Plant-Derived Bioactive Peptides: A Review. *Foods* 11: 2361. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11152361>
- Manna SL, Natale CD, Florio D, Marasco D (2018) Peptides as Therapeutic Agents for Inflammatory-Related Diseases. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms19092714>
- National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (2023) Inflammation. <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/health/topics/conditions/inflammation/index.cfm>
- Raker VK, Becker C, Steinbrink K (2016) The cAMP Pathway as Therapeutic Target in Autoimmune and Inflammatory Diseases. *Frontiers in Immunology* 7: 123. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2016.00123>
- Ramamoorthy S, Cidlowski JA (2016) Corticosteroids-Mechanisms of Action in Health and Disease. *Rheumatic diseases clinics of North America* 42: 15–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rdc.2015.08.002>
- Selige J, Hatzelmann A, Dunkern T (2011) The differential impact of PDE4 subtypes in human lung fibroblasts on cytokine-induced proliferation and myofibroblast conversion. *Journal of Cellular Physiology* 226: 1970–1980. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcp.22529>
- St. Laurent CD, St. Laurent KE, Mathison RD, Befus AD (2015) Calcium-binding protein, spermatid-specific 1 is expressed in human salivary glands and contains an anti-inflammatory motif. *American Journal of Physiology – Regulatory, Integrative and Comparative Physiology* 308: 569–575. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.00153.2014>
- Tavares LP, Negreiros-Lima GL, Lima KM, E Silva PMR, Pinho V, Teixeira MM, Sousa LP (2020) Blame the signaling: Role of cAMP for the resolution of inflammation. *Pharmacological Research* 159: 105030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phrs.2020.105030>
- Tonolo F, Lima Silva RC, Bortoluzzi M, Scarel-Caminaga RM, Vianello F (2025) Antimicrobial and Anti-Inflammatory Bioactive Peptides: Their Role in Potential Therapeutic Applications for Periodontitis-A Narrative Review. *Nutrients* 17: 3105. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu17193105>
- Wang L, Wang N, Zhang W, Cheng X, Yan Z, Shao G, Wang X, Wang R, Fu C (2022) Therapeutic peptides: current applications and future directions. *Signal Transduction and Targeted Therapy* 7: 48. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41392-022-00904-4>

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Anti-inflammatory assay with animals was approved by the Animal Health and Welfare Directorate of the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, based on the position of the Ethics Committee, Bulgarian Food Safety Agency, Protocol No. 419/20.12.2024

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

Funding

This study was funded by the European Union program “Research, Innovation and Digitalisation for Smart Transformation” 2021–2027, project BG16RF-PR002-1.009-0003, “ABC-BIO-CAR.”

Author contributions

Conceptualization, D.D., H.Z.-T., A.M. and S.G.; methodology, H.Z.-T., V.N., M.L.-C., A.M. and S.G.; software, B.B. and V.N.; validation, H.Z.-T., M.L.-C. and S.G.; formal analysis, P.R., B.B., H.Z.-T., M.L.-C. and V.N.; investigation, B.B., H.Z.-T., M.L.-C. and V.N.; resources, D.D.; data curation, H.Z.-T., M.L.-C. and S.G.; writing-original draft preparation, B.B., H.Z.-T. and D.D.; writing-review and editing, M.L.-C., S.G., P.R., A.M. and D.D.; visualization, H.Z.-T., B.B. and V.N.; supervision, M.L.-C., S.G. and D.D.; project administration, D.D.; funding acquisition, P.R., D.D., H.Z.-T., S.G. and B.B.

Author ORCIDs

B. Borisova [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5604-993X) <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5604-993X>

V. Nemska [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8132-831X) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8132-831X>

H. Zlatanova-Tenisheva [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2555-4600) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2555-4600>

M. Laronze-Cochard [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0512-792X) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0512-792X>

S. Gérard [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8307-9986) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8307-9986>

P. Romanova [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1046-1608) <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1046-1608>

A.N. Moulas [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4681-6174) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4681-6174>

D. Danalev [ORCID](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1193-7379) <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1193-7379>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.